

Research article

New records of Psocodea (Insecta) from Guadeloupe, Lesser Antilles

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Abstract: We report 20 species of Psocodea collected in Guadeloupe (Lesser Antilles) during August 2025. Ten are new to the department, and for the Lesser Antilles as a whole. Several species previously known from Guadeloupe are here confirmed with precise localities and GPS coordinates. Five species are recorded for the first time from Grande-Terre Island and four from Basse-Terre Island. With these additions, the checklist of Psocodea from Guadeloupe now comprises 29 species, significantly expanding current knowledge of the Caribbean fauna of this insect order.

Keywords: biodiversity, Caribbean, equatorial, habitats, insects

Introduction

The first publication on Psocodea from Guadeloupe dates back 46 years. At that time, Badonnel (1979) described *Ectopsocus thibaudi* Badonnel, 1979 from Terre-de-Haut Island in the Les Saintes Archipelago, also reporting it from several additional localities. This was followed by the work of the same author, Badonnel (1981), on geophilous psocids, in which he recorded as new for the Guadeloupe area *Echmepteryx lumulata* Thornton, Lee & Chui, 1972, *Lepolepis caribensis* Turner, 1975, *Psocatropos microps* (Enderlein, 1903), *Liposcelis entomophila* (Enderlein, 1907), *Ectopsocus maindroni* Badonnel, 1935, *E. titschacki* Jentsch, 1939, and *Hemipsocus roseus* (Hagen, 1859). Five years later, the species *Peripsocus potosi* Mockford, 1971 was reported, when Badonnel (1986) described gynandromorphism in this species. Subsequently, a new species to science, *Tapinella dichromoptera* Badonnel, 1988, was described from Basse-Terre Island (Badonnel 1988). One year later, Badonnel (1989) reported three species from Guadeloupe with type localities outside the department: *Indiopsocus*

obrieni Badonnel, 1989, *I. etiennei* Badonnel, 1989, and *I. caraibensis* Badonnel, 1989. The most recent article, published 24 years ago, was that of García-Aldrete (1991), who described a new species from the area, namely *Lachesilla caribe* García-Aldrete, 1991. After this period, during which a total of 14 species of psocids were reported, no further studies of these insects have been conducted in Guadeloupe.

This year, however, the authors investigated the fauna of La Désirade Island, from which they reported four species of psocids, among which *Liposcelis bostrychophila* Badonnel, 1931 was a new record to the department (Georgiev & Mishev, 2025).

In the present paper, we report an additional 13 species new to the area (some of them new records for the Lesser Antilles as a whole), as well as new localities for previously known ones.

Material and methods

Barkflies were collected between 09.08.2025 and 19.08.2025 from Guadeloupe, Lesser Antilles. All specimens were collected by beating vegetation

Fig. 1. Some of the Psocodea habitats surveyed during present study: A – a patch of *Heliconia* sp. in a primary rainforest, B – *Etiligera elatior* in a bush area near a road (both on Basse-Terre Island), C – trees and bushes along a dirt road in agricultural and pasture lands, D – *Musa* sp. plantation (both on Grande-Terre Island).

above a white plastic tray or sieving, with a fine brush then preserved in 96% ethanol. Identification was based on the original descriptions and identification keys provided by Gurney (1939), Badonnel (1946, 1955, 1977, 1981), Mockford (1953, 1974, 1993), Smithers (1965), Thornton et al. (1972), Turner (1975), Vaughan et al. (1991), and Lienhard (1998). Distributional data follows mainly Badonnel (1981) and Lienhard (2016).

Abbreviations used: BT – Basse-Terre Island, GT – Grande-Terre Island.

Results and discussion

A total of 20 species were identified as follows (** – new record for the Lesser Antilles, * – new record for a particular island).

Lepidopsocidae

Echmepteryx falco (Badonnel, 1949)**

Material examined: 11.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°13'43.0"N 61°22'30.5"W, 8 m a.s.l., 2 ♀♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 14.08.2025, GT, near Le Moule, agricultural lands, 16°18'46.7"N 61°22'12.7"W, 23 m a.s.l., banana plantation (Fig. 1, D), 12 ♀♀, from dry *Musa* sp. leaves, collected by beating; 17.08.2025, BT, near Marche Vernou path, 16°10'06.0"N 61°40'08.3"W, rainforest, 253 m a.s.l., 4 ♀♀, from dry leaves of *Heliconia* sp., collected by beating; 18.08.2025, GT, near Morne-à-l'Eau, 16°20'41.2"N 61°28'07.8"W, 4 m a.s.l., bushes and trees along dirt road in agricultural and pasture lands, 2 ♀♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating. Remark: Known

Fig. 2. Head markings of two species from the genus *Echmepteryx* registered during present study: A – *E. pallida*, female, 11.08.2025, GT, Pointe Tarare, coastal xeric forest (the characteristic posterior circle of the lunulate marking is indicated by an arrow); B – *E. cf. submontana*, female, 11.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest (green eyes and the absence of a dark stripe below the antennal socket, indicated by an arrow, differ from the original description of *E. submontana*).

from Ivory Coast; Antigua, Brazil, Cuba, French Guiana, Guyana, Madagascar, Mexico, Panama, Puerto Rico, Suriname, Trinidad, USA (Lienhard, 2016). New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Echmepteryx madagascariensis (Kolbe, 1885)**

Material examined: 11.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°13'43.0"N 61°22'30.5"W, 8 m a.s.l., 2 ♀♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 14.08.2025, same locality, 1 ♀, from dry palm leaves, collected by beating. Remark: Pantropical species (Lienhard, 2016). New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Echmepteryx pallida Smithers, 1965**

Material examined: 11.08.2025, GT, Pointe Tarare, coastal xeric forest, 16°15'19.5"N 61°11'54.6"W, 12 m a.s.l., 1 ♀ (Fig. 2A), from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 17.08.2025, GT, E of Sainte-Anne, coastal wet forest, 16°13'55.8"N 61°22'15.3"W, 3 m a.s.l., 1 ♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating. Remark: The species is very similar to *Echmepteryx lunulata* Thornton, Lee & Chui, 1972 (Thornton et al., 1972), which was also reported for Guadeloupe (Badonnel, 1981). We suppose both could be conspecific due to their very slight differences in head markings, according original description of Thornton et al. (1972). However, our material corresponds with the description of Smithers (1965), having a median circle posterior to the lunulate marking in front of the head (Fig. 2A), absent in *E. lunulata* (Thornton et al., 1972). New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Echmepteryx cf. submontana Turner, 1975**

Material examined: 11.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°13'43.0"N 61°22'30.5"W, 8 m a.s.l., 2 ♀♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating (Fig. 2B). Remark: In the specimens we examined, the pattern is more distinct and pronounced, the eyes are green with a brown stripe, and the dark stripe below the antennal socket is absent (Fig. 2B). Darkening of the eyes over time and fading of the head pattern may occur after prolonged preservation of Turner's specimens in ethanol (14 months), but the absence of the stripe in our fresh individuals cannot be attributed to preservation. Future studies, including genetic analyses, would clarify whether the Jamaican and Guadeloupean specimens represent the same species or two distinct taxa. New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Soa flaviterminata Enderlein, 1906**

Material examined: 14.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°13'43.0"N 61°22'30.5"W, 8 m a.s.l., 1 ♀, from leaf litter, collected by sieving. Remark: Widely distributed in tropical and subtropical areas with a closest locality in Cuba (Lienhard, 2016). New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Liposcelididae

Belaphotroctes ghesquierei Badonnel, 1949**

Material examined: 16.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°13'43.0"N 61°22'30.5"W, 8 m a.s.l., 1 ♀, from dry tree bark, collected by sieving.

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Remark: The species was known from Angola, Brazil, Canary Islands, Colombia, Congo, Cuba, Ivory Coast, Madagascar, Mexico, and USA (Lienhard, 2016). New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Liposcelis entomophila (Enderlein, 1907)*

Material examined: 14.08.2025, GT, near Le Moule, agricultural lands, 16°18'46.7"N 61°22'12.7"W, 23 m a.s.l., banana plantation, 1 ♀, from dry *Musa* sp. leaves, collected by beating. Remark: Cosmopolitan species reported from Basse-Terre Island by Badonnel (1981). New record for Grande-Terre Island.

Tapinellidae

Tapinella dichromoptera Badonnel, 1988*

Material examined: 14.08.2025, GT, near Le Moule, agricultural lands, 16°18'46.7"N 61°22'12.7"W, 23 m a.s.l., banana plantation, 2 ♀♀, from dry *Musa* sp. leaves, collected by beating; 19.08.2025, BT, near Bras David River, 16°12'48.3"N 61°39'46.0"W, 123 m a.s.l., rainforest, 3 ♀♀, from dry leaves (including *Heliconia* sp.) (Fig. 1A), collected by beating. Remark: Previously known only from its type locality, Basse-Terre Island, at Petit-Bourg, (Badonnel, 1988). New record for Grande-Terre Island. The specimens we collected have brown eyes, rather than black as described. This character is typical of the closely related *T. montjoliensis* Georgiev, 2023, known from French Guiana (Georgiev, 2023a), which may prove conspecific following future studies, particularly genetic analyses. The rather subtle differences between the two species include slightly darker, blackish-brown eyes in some specimens of *T. dichromoptera*, as well as the lacinia, in which the length difference between the two cusps is somewhat greater. We also observed differences between our Guadeloupean specimens and the illustrations provided by Badonnel – the apices of the lacinial cusps are rounded and not as widely separated, and, as noted above, the eye colour is brown rather than black.

Tapinella maculata Mockford & Gurney, 1976

Material examined: 14.08.2025, GT, near Le Moule, agricultural lands, 16°18'46.7"N 61°22'12.7"W, 23 m a.s.l., banana plantation, 1 ♀, from dry *Musa* sp. leaves, collected by beating. Remark: The species

was reported for Guadeloupe without an exact locality (Badonnel, 1988). We provide the first record of the species with precise GPS coordinates.

Tapinella sp.

Material examined: 19.08.2025, BT, near Bras David River, 16°12'48.3"N 61°39'46.0"W, 123 m a.s.l., rainforest, 3 ♀♀, from dry leaves (including *Heliconia* sp.), collected by beating. Remark: All three specimens we collected are micropterous and occur in sympatry with *T. dichromoptera*. Badonnel (1988) reported a similar form of *dichromoptera*, and even earlier (Badonnel, 1981) referred to it as *T. olmeca* Mockford, 1975, a widespread species occurring in Mexico, Belize, and Panama (Mockford, 1975). However, our specimens differ in colouration from both *dichromoptera* and *olmeca*. Future studies will determine whether they represent a species new to science or belong to one of the already known taxa.

Ectopsocidae

Ectopsocus maindroni Badonnel, 1935*

Material examined: 09.08.2025, GT, near Anse a la Barque, 16°15'10.9"N 61°19'47.0"W, 17 m a.s.l., bushes, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂, from dry vegetation, collected by beating. Remark: Cosmopolitan species (Lienhard, 2016), reported for Basse Terre Island, the area of Morne Claire Fontaine (Badonnel, 1981) and La Desirade Island, near Plage des Galets (Georgiev & Mishev, 2025). New record for Grande-Terre Island.

Ectopsocus titschacki Jentsch, 1939*

Material examined: 11.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°13'43.0"N 61°22'30.5"W, 8 m a.s.l., 1 ♂, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 14.08.2025, GT, near Le Moule, agricultural lands, 16°18'46.7"N 61°22'12.7"W, 23 m a.s.l., banana plantation, 1 ♀, 1 ♂, from dry *Musa* sp. leaves, collected by beating; 17.08.2025, BT, near Marche Vernou path, 16°10'06.0"N 61°40'08.3"W, rainforest, 253 m a.s.l., from dry leaves of *Heliconia* sp., 1 ♂, collected by beating; 16.08.2025, BT, Plage de Viard, Petit-Bourg, 16°09'53.3"N 61°35'05.6"W, 6 m a.s.l., 1 ♂, from various vegetation, littoral bush area covered with *Sargassum* seaweed, collected by

beating; 19.08.2025, BT, near Bras David River, 16°12'48.3"N 61°39'46.0"W, 123 m a.s.l., rainforest, 3 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂, from dry leaves (including *Heliconia* sp.), collected by beating. Remark: Reported for Marie-Galante Island, Pres Ancien Moulin Gran Pierre (Badonnel, 1981). New record for Basse-Terre and Grande-Terre Islands.

Ectopsocus thibaudi Badonnel, 1979*

Material examined: 09.08.2025, GT, N of Plage de Bois Jolan, 16°14'20.5"N 61°21'04.1"W, 12 m a.s.l., banana plantation, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂, from dry banana leaves, collected by beating; 09.08.2025, GT, near Anse a la Barque, 16°15'10.9"N 61°19'47.0"W, 17 m a.s.l., bushes, 5 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 10.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, bushes at forest edge, 16°13'59.6"N 61°22'30.2"W, 18 m a.s.l., 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 11.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°13'43.0"N 61°22'30.5"W, 8 m a.s.l., 4 ♀♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 14.08.2025, same locality, 2 ♀♀, from dry palm leaves, collected by beating; 12.08.2025, BT, near Saut de la Lezarde, 16°10'16.5"N 61°39'48.0"W, bushes, 223 m a.s.l., 3 ♂♂, from dry leaves of *Etilingera elatior* (Fig. 1, B), collected by beating; 14.08.2025, GT, near Le Moule, agricultural lands, 16°18'46.7"N 61°22'12.7"W, 23 m a.s.l., banana plantation, 4 ♀♀, 1 ♂, from dry *Musa* sp. leaves, collected by beating; 15.08.2025, BT, N of Plage de Petite Anse, 16°06'02.8"N 61°46'17.3"W, 22 m a.s.l., coastal bushes, 2 ♀♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 16.08.2025, BT, Plage de Viard, Petit-Bourg, 16°09'53.3"N 61°35'05.6"W, 6 m a.s.l., 12 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, from various vegetation, littoral bush area covered with *Sargassum* seaweed, collected by beating; 17.08.2025, GT, E of Sainte-Anne, coastal wet forest, 16°13'55.8"N 61°22'15.3"W, 3 m a.s.l., 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 18.08.2025, BT, near Plage Manbia, St. Rose, 16°20'49.9"N 61°43'13.3"W, 8 m a.s.l., coastal bushes, 15 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 18.08.2025, GT, near Morne-à-l'Eau, 16°20'41.2"N 61°28'07.8"W, 4 m a.s.l., bushes and trees along dirt road in agricultural and pasture lands (Fig. 1C), 1 ♂, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 19.08.2025, BT, near Bras David River, 16°12'48.3"N 61°39'46.0"W, 123 m a.s.l., rainforest, 3 ♀♀, 1 ♂, from dry leaves (including *Heliconia* sp.),

collected by beating. Remark: Known from Terre-de-Haut Island (type locality), Grande-Terre Island, Marie-Galante Island, and La Desirade Island (Badonnel, 1979, 1981; Georgiev & Mishev, 2025). New record for Basse-Terre Island.

Ectopsocus vilhenai Badonnel, 1955*

Material examined: 14.08.2025, GT, near Le Moule, agricultural lands, 16°18'46.7"N 61°22'12.7"W, 23 m a.s.l., banana plantation, 1 ♂, from dry *Musa* sp. leaves, collected by beating; 18.08.2025, BT, near Plage Manbia, St. Rose, 16°20'49.9"N 61°43'13.3"W, 8 m a.s.l., coastal bushes, 1 ♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating. Remark: Known from Marie-Galante Island (Badonnel, 1981). New record for Basse-Terre and Grande-Terre Islands.

Lachesillidae

Lachesilla dilatiforceps García-Aldrete, 1996**

Material examined: 12.08.2025, BT, near Saut de la Lezarde, 16°10'16.5"N 61°39'48.0"W, 223 m a.s.l., bushes, 1 ♂, from dry leaves of *Etilingera elatior*, collected by beating; 15.08.2025, BT, N of Plage de Petite Anse, 16°06'02.8"N 61°46'17.3"W, 22 m a.s.l., coastal bushes, 2 ♀♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating. Remark: The species *L. dilatiforceps* is reported for Puerto Rico, Dominican Republic and Haiti (García-Aldrete, 1996). New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Archipsocidae

Archipsocopsis cubana Badonnel, 1977**

Material examined: 09.08.2025, GT, near Anse a la Barque, 16°15'10.9"N 61°19'47.0"W, 17 m a.s.l., bushes, 3 ♀♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 13.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°14'13.7"N 61°22'41.8"W, 24 m a.s.l., 1 ♀, from dry tree bark, collected by sieving; 18.08.2025, BT, near Plage Manbia, St. Rose, 16°20'49.9"N 61°43'13.3"W, 8 m a.s.l., coastal bushes, 1 ♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating; 19.08.2025, BT, near Bras David River, 16°12'48.3"N 61°39'46.0"W, 123 m a.s.l., rainforest,

4 ♀♀, from dry leaves (including *Heliconia* sp.), collected by beating. Remark: The species *A. cubana* is very similar to *A. machadoi* (Badonnel, 1955). One of the differences is the length of fl of the antennae, which in *A. cubana* is longer than P, and shorter in *machadoi*. This species was known only from Cuba (Badonnel, 1977). New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Archipsocus nomas Gurney, 1939**

Material examined: 16.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°13'43.0"N 61°22'30.5"W, 8 m a.s.l., 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, from dry tree bark, collected by sieving. Remark: The species was known from Bermuda Islands, Cuba, Mexico and USA (Lienhard, 2016). New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Pseudocaeciliidae

Pseudocaecilius clunialis Vaughan, Thornton & New, 1991**

Material examined: 14.08.2025, GT, near Le Moule, agricultural lands, 16°18'46.7"N 61°22'12.7"W, 23 m a.s.l., banana plantation, 8 ♀♀, from dry *Musa* sp. leaves, collected by beating. Remark: The species was known only from Indonesia (Vaughan et al., 1991) and recently found in French Guiana (Georgiev, 2023b). New record for the Caribbean and second record for the New World.

Hemipsocidae

Hemipsocus pretiosus Banks, 1930**

Material examined: 11.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, 16°13'43.0"N 61°22'30.5"W, 8 m a.s.l., secondary rainforest, 4 ♀♀, from dry vegetation and leaf litter, collected by beating; 14.08.2025, same locality, 2 ♀♀, from leaf litter, collected by sieving; 13.08.2025, GT, Sainte-Anne, secondary rainforest, 16°14'13.7"N 61°22'41.8"W, 24 m a.s.l., 1 ♀, from dry vegetation, collected by beating. Remark: According the redescription of Mockford (1974) the compound eyes of this species are black. In the fresh specimens collected the actual colour was green. The species was known from Cuba, Mexico

and USA (Lienhard, 2016). New record for the Lesser Antilles.

Hemipsocus roseus (Hagen, 1859)*

Material examined: 17.08.2025, BT, near Marche Vernou path, 16°10'06.0"N 61°40'08.3"W, rainforest, 253 m a.s.l., from dry leaves of *Heliconia* sp., 7 ♀♀, collected by beating; 19.08.2025, BT, near Bras David River, 16°12'48.3"N 61°39'46.0"W, 123 m a.s.l., rainforest, 1 ♀, from dry leaves (including *Heliconia* sp.), collected by beating. Remark: Reported for Guadeloupe from Grande-Terre Island at Pointe d'Enfer by Badonnel (1981). New record for Basse-Terre Island.

Of the 20 species recorded by us, 11 are reported for the first time from the Lesser Antilles. Two species previously known from the region, but without precise localities, are confirmed here, with coordinates of the collection sites provided. All seven remaining species are reported from one or more islands of the department. Five species are newly reported from Grande-Terre, and four from Basse-Terre.

The present study reveals a diversity of Psocodea species across different habitats on the islands of Grande-Terre and Basse-Terre in Guadeloupe. The species composition varies depending on the habitat type, but it is clear that the collected specimens prefer dry microhabitats. This includes dry leaves, tree bark, and leaf litter. The greatest species richness was observed in secondary rainforests, where seven species were found, including several new to the Antilles, such as *E. falco*, *E. madagascariensis*, *E. cf. submontana*, *S. flaviterminata*, *B. ghesquierei*, *A. nomas*, and *H. pretiosus*. A significant presence of species was also noted in plantations and agricultural lands. Here, species such as *E. titschacki*, *T. dichromoptera*, *E. vilhenai*, and *P. clunialis* were found. These species are possibly adapted to cultivated environments, where they were collected mainly from the dry leaves of banana plants (*Musa* sp.). Coastal forests and shrublands also support their own species composition. For example, *E. pallida* was found in both a coastal xeric forest and a coastal wet forest. Species such as *E. thibaudi* and *L. cf. dilatiforceps* were recorded in coastal bushes. *E. thibaudi* was also collected from a littoral bush area covered with *Sargassum* seaweed, highlighting its adaptability to various coastal conditions.

Updated check list of the Psocodea species known from Guadeloupe (29 species known)

Lepidopsocidae

1. *Echmepteryx falco* (Badonnel, 1949): present publication
2. *Echmepteryx lumulata* Thornton, Lee & Chui, 1972: Marie-Galante Island, 2 km NW of Grande Bourg (Badonnel, 1981)
3. *Echmepteryx madagascariensis* (Kolbe, 1885): present publication
4. *Echmepteryx pallida* Smithers, 1965: present publication
5. *Echmepteryx* cf. *submontana* Turner, 1975: present publication
6. *Soa flaviterminata* Enderlein, 1906: present publication
7. *Lepolepis caribensis* Turner, 1975: Marie-Galante Island, near Bois d'Inde Bay (Badonnel, 1981)

Psyllipsocidae

8. *Psocatropos microps* (Enderlein, 1903): Basse-Terre Island, Coreil, 5 km from Bouillante and Trace V. Hugues at 1050 m altitude (Badonnel, 1981)

Liposcelididae

9. *Belaphotroctes ghesquierei* Badonnel, 1949: present publication
10. *Liposcelis bostrychophila* Badonnel, 1931: east coast of La Desirade Island (Georgiev & Mishev, 2025)
11. *Liposcelis entomophila* (Enderlein, 1907): Basse-Terre Island, Trace V. Hugues and near As de Pique Lake at altitude 740 m (Badonnel, 1981); present publication

Tapinellidae

12. *Tapinella dichromoptera* Badonnel, 1988: Basse-Terre Island, at Petit-Bourg, type locality of the species (Badonnel, 1988); present publication
13. *Tapinella maculata* Mockford & Gurney, 1976: Guadeloupe (Badonnel, 1988)
14. *Tapinella* sp.: present publication

Lachesillidae

15. *Lachesilla caribe* García-Aldrete, 1991: Guadeloupe, Basse-Terre Island, Sofaia, 6 km SW Sainte Rose (type locality), Fefe Forest, ca. Capesterre (García-Aldrete, 1991)
16. *Lachesilla dilatiforceps* García-Aldrete, 1996: present publication

Ectopsocidae

17. *Ectopsocus maindroni* Badonnel, 1935: Basse-Terre Island, the area of Morne Claire Fontaine (Badonnel, 1981); La Desirade Island, near Plage des Galets (Georgiev & Mishev, 2025); present publication
18. *Ectopsocus titschacki* Jentsch, 1939: Marie-Galante Island, Pres Ancien Moulin Gran Pierre (Badonnel, 1981); present publication
19. *Ectopsocus thibaudi* Badonnel, 1979: Terre-de-Haut Island from the Les Saintes Archipelago (type locality), Grande-Terre Island, near Caraïbe du Moile Cave, Marie-Galante Island, near Grand Trou à Diable Cave (Badonnel, 1979); Marie-Galante Island, Chateau Murat (Badonnel, 1981); east, west and middle area of La Desirade Island (Georgiev & Mishev, 2025); present publication
20. *Ectopsocus vilhenai* Badonnel, 1955: Marie-Galante Island, Vers Grand Fond, 3 km NE of Capesterre (Badonnel, 1981); present publication

Peripsocidae

21. *Peripsocus potosi* Mockford, 1971: "Guadeloupe, Duclos", probably on Basse-Terre Island (Badonnel, 1986)

Archipsocidae

22. *Archipsocopsis cubana* Badonnel, 1977: present publication
23. *Archipsocus nomas* Gurney, 1939: present publication

Pseudocaeciliidae

24. *Pseudocaecilius chunialis* Vaughan, Thornton & New, 1991: present publication

Hemipsocidae

25. *Hemipsocus pretiosus* Banks, 1930: present publication
26. *Hemipsocus roseus* (Hagen, 1859): Grande-Terre Island, Pointe d'Enfer (Badonnel, 1981); present publication

Psocidae

27. *Indiopsocus caraibensis* Badonnel, 1989: Basse-Terre Island, near Matouba at Soufriere (Badonnel, 1989)
28. *Indiopsocus etiennei* Badonnel, 1989: Basse-Terre Island, Baillif (Badonnel, 1989)
29. *Indiopsocus obrieni* Badonnel, 1989: Grande-Terre Island, Port Louise (Badonnel, 1989)

Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the author, reviewers, or subject editor.

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